

GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A TOOL USED IN ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE SURVEILLANCE

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Geographical information system (GIS) is a tool allowing to show geographical dependencies in order to better interpretation of the obtained results (1). The aim of the study was to use GIS for mapping the results of AMR *Escherichia coli* obtained within official monitoring acc. to Decision 2013/652/EC in Poland in 2018.

METHODS

The input data accounted for localisation places of origin of broiler and turkey flocks, at the level of municipalities, were obtained from General Veterinary Inspectorate and the tests results were obtained from National Reference Laboratory for AMR (Dept. of Microbiology, NVRI). Data on occurrence of indicator *E. coli*, *E. coli* producing ESBL or AmpC, and carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* were presented on maps generated using ArcGIS 10.4.1 (ESRI) (Fig.1).

RESULTS

- Maps showing that places of sample collections were spread all over the country.
- The number of indicator *E. coli* isolates per municipality for broilers oscillated between 1 and 16 and for turkeys – between 1 and 20.
- For both broiler and turkey flocks, most of indicator *E. coli* were located in the western part of Poland, but the main localisation of isolates was in the north of the country.
- For *E. coli* producing ESBL or AmpC isolated from broilers the number of isolates per municipality was from 1 to 5 isolates while for turkeys from 1 to 11.
- For both broiler and turkey flocks, most of *E. coli* producing ESBL or AmpC, were located in the same municipality located in the western part of Poland.
- In the case of carbapenemase-producing *E. coli* no positive results were found both for broilers and turkeys.

Fig1 GIS mapping of the results of AMR *Escherichia coli* isolated from broiler and turkey flocks.

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

GIS mapping of AMR surveillance results revealed usefulness of the tool. The visualisation of geographical information might give stakeholders and scientists the possibility to locate problematic areas.

REFERENCES

Kirby, R. S. et al, *Annals of Epidemiology* 2017, 27, 1-9

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